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Research Article

TREND OF BREAST FEEDING IN OUR SOCIETY¹Dr. Raza Ali Saif, ²Dr. Hafiza Bushra Ghani, ³Dr. Sayyam Fatima¹Sahiwal Medical College Sahiwal Punjab Pakistan²Nishtar Hospital Multan³Holy Family Hospital Rwp**Abstract**

Introduction: Breastfeeding is very important for child growth it's the first gift of mother to a child the children who are breast fed maintain their health we conduct a study to know about how many mother breast fed their children and know its importance.

Objective: aims and objective behind this research are to know the trend of breast feeding in society and to aware the mothers the importance of breastfeeding

Research and methodology: it was a cohort study. Sample data was selected by randomized trial

Venue: DHQ Teaching Hospital Sahiwal Punjab Pakistan

Conclusion: 20% Percent mothers don't breastfeed their neonates 30% percent women quit breastfeeding before 2 years: Children who were not breastfed properly, were not healthy and became sick off and on.

Keywords: Breastfeeding, weaning, child body growth, low weight for age.

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INTRODUCTION:

Breastfeeding is a natural gift for child. It not only provides a balanced diet to a new born but also provides immunity against many diseases. Unfortunately most of mothers don't know its importance especially in our society. We decided to make a research to know about ground realities about breastfeeding in our society. Research was conducted at peads OPD DHQ teaching hospital Sahiwal in friendly environment by taking consent of parents

Objectives

There are two main objectives

- i) To know about ground realities of breast feeding trend in our society
- ii) To educate mothers the importance of breastfeeding

Literature Review**Importance of Breastfeeding**

WHO has recommended that pregnant women and new mothers be informed of the benefits of and superiority of breast feeding especially of early nutrition and exclusive breastfeeding for 6 months in particular the fact that it provides the best nutrition and protect babies from diarrhea and other illness. Mothers should be given guidance on the preparation for and maintenance of lactation the art of expressing out breast milk, its storage and feeding it to infant with special emphasis on the importance of well-balanced diet both during pregnancy and after delivery. Unnecessary induction of partial bottefeeding or other foodsand drinks should be discouraged since it will have negative effect on breastfeeding as well as health of the infants.similarly

mothers should bewarned of the difficuly of reversal of decision not to breastfedeven if bottle feed is limitedto a few bottlesbefore advising the mother to use an infant formula she should be advised too the social and economical implications of her decision.

Research design and methodology**Study design**

It is cross sectional type of study

Venue

OPD peads department DHQ teaching hospital Sahiwal

Data collection

A randomly self designed questionnaire was used to collect data from parents in opd

Questionnaire

A structured questionnaire was formulated after extensive struggle and hard working

It comprises of two portions;

- i) 1st portion contains name,father name,age and introduction
- ii) 2nd portion contains questions related to breastfeeding

Inclusion criteria

All the children presented in opd

Exclusion criteria

Parents who refused to give consent or children in a critical condition not included in research

Sample size

Total sample size of 200 patients

Ethics approval

Prior to questionnaire, informed consent was obtained from parents after assuring confidentiality

Data presentation, analysis and interpretation**1.Demographic data****i) age groups**

Age group	number	percent
<2 years	92	51
>2 years	89	49

ii)male to female

Gender	number	percent
Male	100	55
Female	81	45

2.Educational data

- i) How many mothers breastfed their children?

80% mothers breastfeeding their children

ii) how many mothers quit breastfeeding before 2 years?

30% mothers quit breastfeeding before 2 years

iii).Mothers who are not breastfeeding what milk used for their children?

70% used cow or buffalo milk

13% used powder milk

17% used mixed cow and powder milk

General considerations

- i) This research was introductory to know about the parents education level about breastfeeding
- ii) Children who were >2 years were inquired about their breastfeeding in childhood
- iii) Children who were newborn we inquired from their mothers to know about what they plan for feeding of child in future

DISCUSSION:

Research was conducted in peaceful and friendly environment .we surprised and sad to know about the literacy level of mothers especially in rural area of society .many mothers don't know the importance of breastfeeding .there is need to educate the mothers about this hot issue. government and other welfare organisations should play its role for improvement of our child health.

CONCLUSION:

After all this we concluded that;

1. 20% Percent mothers don't breastfeed their neonates.
2. 30% percent women quit breastfeeding before 2 years.
3. Children who were not breastfed properly were not healthy and became sick off and on.
4. Mothers who don't breastfeed their children, its causes include misconceptions 41%, 2nd pregnancy 50% and 9% others like congenital defect or sickness.

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